

Spectrophotometric Study of the Binary System Tantalum(v)-Solochrom Violet RS and Determination of Tantalum(v)

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A simple and direct spectrophotometric method for determination of Ta^V has been developed using solochrom violet RS. The Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.3619–10.857 µg/ml of Ta^V. The effects of various parameters including time, pH and added reactant volume have been studied.

Several azo compounds¹ have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of tantalum(v). The present work reports the use of the azo compound solochrom violet RS (sodium salt of 2-hydroxynaphthyl-azo-1-phenol-4-sulphonic acid) for the spectrophotometric determination of Ta^V.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between the Ta^V and the azo compound results in the formation of a red colored complex, which shows an absorption maximum at 560 nm where the reagent absorbs negligibly. The effect of time, reactant volume and pH on the determination of Ta^V was studied. The optimum time required for development of color was found to be 10 min at room temperature. The effect of the concentration of the reagent was examined. For 1 ml solution of Ta^V (10⁻³ M), 3 ml of solochrom violet RS solution (10⁻³ M) was sufficient. The absorbance remained practically constant above this value. The formation of the complex was studied over a wide pH range 2.12–6.5 using buffer solutions. The result indicates that the absorbance was maximum in the acid domain at pH 5.6.

The composition of the Ta^V-solochrom complex was established using Job's method² of continuous variation and mole-ratio method. The mole ratio was found to be 1 : 3. The stability constant of the complex was calculated using non-isomolar series method², $K = 4.6494 \cdot 10^{12}$ ($pK = 11.328 \pm 0.023$) for a 95% probability at 25° temperature and ionic strength $\mu = 0.4$. The average value of the stability constant indicates a good stability of the complex.

The charge of the complex ion was determined by electrophoretic migration method in the presence of a weak solution of potassium nitrate. After 12 min, the colored complex ion migrated towards the anode indicating the complex ion to be negatively charged. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.3619–10.857 µg Ta^V/ml.

For testing the validity of the method, the experimental data were statistically interpreted through the linear regression method³. The correlation coefficient (r) having the value of 0.9999 indicates a linear dependence of the absorbance on the Ta^V concentration. The method proposed for

the determination of Ta^V is reproducible and accurate, the relative standard deviation being $\pm 1.2\%$, not affected by systemic errors. The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity are $9.10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and 0.020 µg cm^{-2} respectively.

Interference studies demonstrate that the color reaction of Ta^V-solochrom violet RS is specific. Various cations were added individually to a solution of Ta^V (10⁻³ M) and the limits of molar ratios at which Ta^V was recognised were Ta^V:Ti^{IV} = 1 : 10, Ta^V:W^{VI} = 1 : 121, Ta^V:V^V = 1 : 8. The presence of Nb, Zn, Al, Ga, Tl, U and Ru does not disturb due to the different absorption maxima of the respective complexes⁴ (Ta^V:Nb^V = 1 : 250; Ta^V:Zn^{II} = 1 : 225; Ta^V:Al^{III} = 1 : 215; Ta^V:Ga^{III} = 1 : 210; Ta^V:Tl^{III} = 1 : 205; Ta^V:U^{VI} = 1 : 200; Ta^V:Ru^{III} = 1 : 240). Other elements which could interfere with Ta^V can be masked, for example, Zr^{IV} can be masked with EDTA⁵.

Experimental

A Mettler Delta 320 pH-meter and a Zeiss-Jena V.S.U.-2P spectrophotometer were used. All reagents used were of analytical grade. Aqueous solutions (10⁻³ M) of complex oxalate of Ta^V and solochrom violet RS were prepared. Buffer solutions in the pH range 2.12–6.5 were prepared according to Britton-Robinson's method⁶.

Procedure : To a known volume of metal ion solution (10⁻³ M; complex oxalate of Ta^V)⁷, the reagent solution (10⁻³ M; 6 ml) was added. The pH was then adjusted to 5.6 with the appropriate buffer. The absorbance was measured at 560 nm against a reagent blank after 10 min.

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